

Mengenal Indeksasi Nasional & Internasional

Faizal risdianto

Uin salatiga

www.pegijatjurnal.com

1. **Jumlah Kunjungan Unik ke Laman**

- >50 kunjungan unik ke laman rerata per hari untuk jurnal yang terbit (Skor 3.0)
- 10-50 kunjungan unik ke laman rerata per hari untuk jurnal yang terbit (Skor 2.0)
- <10 kunjungan unik ke laman rerata per hari untuk jurnal yang terbit (Skor 1.0)

2. **Pencantuman di Lembaga Pengindeks**

- Tercantum di lembaga pengindeks internasional bereputasi (Skor 8.0)
- Tercantum dalam lembaga pengindeks internasional (Skor 6.0)
- Tercantum dalam lembaga pengindeks nasional (Skor 4.0)

3. **Alamat/Identitas Unik Artikel**

- Memiliki DOI tiap artikel (Skor 1.0)
- Memiliki alamat laman yang permanen tiap artikel (Skor 0.5)
- Tidak memiliki DOI ataupun alamat laman permanen (Skor 0.0)

Pembagian Lembaga Pengindeks (Berdasar Aturan Akreditasi)

Rendah

- Google Scholar, ISJD, IPI, World Cat, Moraref dan yang setara.
- Tidak menggunakan kualifikasi tertentu agar bisa terindeks.

Menengah

- DOAJ, REPEC, ERIC, PubMed, EBSCO, Web of Science (ESCI) dan yang setara.
- Memerlukan seleksi kebijakan dan seleksi formal lainnya.

Tinggi

- SCOPUS, Web of Science (SSCI, SCIE), dan yang setara.
- Memerlukan seleksi konten dan kebijakan jurnal.

Indexing level rendah

1. PROFIL GOOGLE SCHOLAR JURNAL
2. PORTAL GARUDA
3. MORAREF
4. CROSSREF SEARCH

<http://scholar.google.com> cara bikin akun log in dengan email resmi jurnal dan add semua naskah yang ada tulisan nama jurnal kita.

The screenshot shows a Google Scholar profile for 'Register Journal'. The profile includes a circular logo, the journal's name, affiliation (IAIN Salatiga), a verified email address, and a list of keywords: ESL, EFL, TEFLIN, TEFL, and Applied linguistics. A 'FOLLOW' button is visible. Below the profile information is a table of cited works with columns for 'TITLE', 'CITED BY', and 'YEAR'. To the right, there is a 'Cited by' section with a table showing 'All' and 'Since 2015' counts for Citations, h-index, and i10-index, along with a bar chart showing the number of citations per year from 2015 to 2022. At the bottom right, there is a 'Co-authors' section listing three individuals with their photos and affiliations.

Register Journal
IAIN Salatiga
Verified email at iainsalatiga.ac.id - [Homepage](#)
ESL EFL TEFLIN TEFL Applied linguistics

FOLLOW

TITLE	CITED BY	YEAR
EFL classes must go online! Teaching activities and challenges during COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia AEP Atmojo, A Nugroho Register Journal 13 (1), 49-76	497	2020
Psychological problems and challenge in EFL speaking classroom WL Arifin Register Journal 10 (1), 29-47	59	2017
The effectiveness of speaking instruction through task-based language teaching N Malihah Register Journal 3 (1), 85-101	47	2010
The implementation of SQ3R method to develop students' reading skill on islamic texts in EFL class in indonesia AG Marzuki Register Journal 12 (1), 49-61	40	2019
The effectiveness of skimming and scanning strategies in improving comprehension and reading speed rates for the students of English study program I Fauzi, FUP Raya	38	2018

Cited by

	All	Since 2015
Citations	1454	139
h-index	16	1
i10-index	30	2

Year	Citations
2015	1
2016	2
2017	3
2018	5
2019	10
2020	20
2021	54
2022	40

Co-authors

- **Faizal Risdianto**
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IAIN Salatiga
- **Win Listyaningrum Arifin**
IAIN Salatiga

Portal GARUDA <https://garuda.kemdikbud.go.id/>

- Portal GARUDA <https://garuda.kemdikbud.go.id/>

Cara mendaftarkan jurnal: <https://garuda.kemdikbud.go.id/suggest>

CROSSREF METADATA SEARCH: TYPE YOUR ISSN OF JOURNAL

Q 2503-040X [Funding Data](#) [Link References](#) [Status](#) [API](#) [Help](#) [Sign in](#)

SORT BY: **RELEVANCE** PUBLICATION YEAR PAGE 1 OF 314 RESULTS

Showing results for ISSN matching 2503-040X

Phonological Analysis of Indian Language
Journal Article published 1 Jun 2012 in Register Journal volume 5 issue 1 on page 1
Authors: Adiprana Yogatama
<https://doi.org/10.18326/rgt.v5i1.249> Actions

The Application of “The Mystery Guest Game” to enhance the Students English Verbal Communication of Grade X-1 of SMA Pabelan in 2010/2011
Journal Article published 1 Jul 2016 in Register Journal volume 4 issue 1
<https://doi.org/10.18326/rgt.v4i1.455> Actions

Comparing the Psychological Aimlessness in Edith Wharton’s the House of Mirth and Ernest Hemmingway’s the Sun also Rises
Journal Article published 1 Jul 2016 in Register Journal volume 3 issue 1 on page 51

<https://search.crossref.org/?q=2503-040X>

Moraref.kemenag.go.id

The screenshot displays the MORAREF website interface. At the top left is the MORAREF logo, and at the top right is a navigation menu with links for Home, Articles, Journals, Announcements, Statistics, Services, and Login. The main content area features a cover image of the Register Journal on the left, which includes the title, ISSN (1979-8903), and a list of articles. To the right of the cover, the journal's title 'REGISTER JOURNAL' is prominently displayed, followed by the publisher 'IAIN Salatiga'. Below this, a table lists key statistics: Articles (198), ISSN (e-ISSN) (1979-8903 (2503-040X)), Grade (M2), and Country (Indonesia). A descriptive paragraph follows, stating that the journal is an open access, peer-reviewed, international ESCI Web of Science indexed journal focusing on formal and functional linguistics and English language teaching. A green 'Visit Website' button is located at the bottom of the journal information section.

MORAREF

Home Articles **Journals** Announcements Statistics Services Login

REGISTER JOURNAL

Published by IAIN Salatiga

Articles	: 198	Grade	: M2
ISSN (e-ISSN)	: 1979-8903 (2503-040X)	Country	: Indonesia

REGISTER JOURNAL, 1979-8903 (PRINT)- 2503-040X (ONLINE) is an OPEN ACCESS, Peer-reviewed, International ESCI Web of Science Indexed Journal has the perspectives of languages and language teachings. This journal has the Focus and Scope of presenting and discussing some outstanding contemporary issues dealing with Formal & Functional Linguistics and English Language Teaching (ELT).

[Visit Website](#)

Indexing kelas menengah

- DOAJ
- DIMENSION
- COPENICUS
- ESCI WOS

<https://doaj.org/toc/2503-040X>

DOAJ OPEN
GLOBAL
TRUSTED

SEARCH ▾ DOCUMENTATION ▾ ABOUT ▾

🕒 UPDATED RECENTLY

Register Journal

Journal Register

📄 1979-8903 (PRINT) / 2503-040X (ONLINE)

[🔗 Website](#) [🔗 ISSN Portal](#)

About [Articles](#)

<https://doaj.org/account/login?redirected=apply>

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the DOAJ website. The logo consists of three overlapping red and orange shapes to the left of the text 'DOAJ'. To the right of 'DOAJ' are the words 'OPEN', 'GLOBAL', and 'TRUSTED' stacked vertically. Further right is a 'SUPP' link. Below the navigation bar are three menu items: 'SEARCH', 'DOCUMENTATION', and 'ABOUT', each with a downward arrow. The main content area has a heading 'Application form' in a bold serif font. Below the heading is a paragraph of text: 'Read our [Guide to applying](#) first. It will help you understand the basic criteria that your journal should meet. If you need help with the application form, please [contact us](#).' Below this is another line of text: 'You can [print or download](#) a PDF preview of the form.' At the bottom of the visible content is the text: 'Log in or register to submit your application.'

DOAJ OPEN
GLOBAL
TRUSTED SUPP

SEARCH ▾ DOCUMENTATION ▾ ABOUT ▾

Application form

Read our [Guide to applying](#) first. It will help you understand the basic criteria that your journal should meet. If you need help with the application form, please [contact us](#).

You can [print or download](#) a PDF preview of the form.

Log in or register to submit your application.

Journal of Pragmatics Research | ICI Journals Master List (indexcopernicus.com)

INDEX COPERNICUS INTERNATIONAL

ICI World of Journals ICI Journals Master List ICI World of Papers Contact Login/ Register

ICI World of Journals / Journal of Pragmatics Research [← Back](#)

Journal of Pragmatics Research

English title: Journal of Pragmatics Research
ISSN: 2656-8020
GICID: *n/d*
DOI: 10.18326/jopr.v3i2.86-96
Website: <http://e-journal.iainsalatiga.ac.id/index.php/jopr>
Publisher: IAIN Salatiga
Country: ID
Language of publication: *n/d*

Deposited publications: 0 > Full text: 0% | Abstract: 0% | Keywords: 0% | References: 0% [Issues and contents](#)

Non-indexed in the ICI Journals Master List 2021

Not reported for evaluation [Archival ratings >](#)

MSHE points: *n/d*

[Archival ratings >](#)

Please contact with:

[✉ The editorial office of the journal](#) (Comments, Requests, Information)

<https://journals.indexcopernicus.com/app/auth/login?language=en>

Sign in

Welcome to the ICI World of Journals system!

Username

Password

Restore password

Sign in

The **ICI World of Journals** is one of the largest international databases of scientific journals. Currently, over 40 thousand journals from all over the world are registered in the database. A special system for managing the account makes it possible to:

- Manage the Journal's Passport
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We remain at your disposal by phone +48 22 487 53 93 or e-mail journals@indexcopernicus.com from Monday to Friday from 8am to 4pm.

Registration

http://app.dimensions.ai/

The screenshot shows the Dimensions app interface for the 'Register Journal'. The top navigation bar includes the Dimensions logo, a search bar with 'Register Journal' entered, and links for 'Save / Export', 'Support', 'Register', and 'Log'. The left sidebar contains 'FILTERS' and 'FAVORITES' sections. The main content area displays 'Register Journal' with a document icon, 'Publications: 314', and 'Datasets: 0'. Below this, there are tabs for 'PUBLICATIONS', 'DATASETS', 'GRANTS', 'PATENTS', and 'CLINICAL TRIALS'. The 'PUBLICATIONS' tab is active, showing 'POLICY DOCUMENTS' and a list of publications. The first publication is 'EFL Teachers' Beliefs and ICT Integration Practices During Distance Learning: Employing Replacement, Amplification, and Transformation Framework' by Anggi Purwa Lestarina, Joko Nurkamto Nurkamto, and Ngadiso Ngadiso Ngadiso, published in 2022 in Register Journal - Article. The right sidebar shows 'ANALYTICAL VIEWS' with 'RESEARCH CATEGORIES' and 'OVERVIEW'. The 'OVERVIEW' section includes a line graph of 'Citations' from 2013 to 2022, showing a peak in 2016 and a mean of 1.05.

Dimensions Register Journal x Save / Export Support Register Log

FILTERS FAVORITES

- > PUBLICATION YEAR
- > RESEARCHER
- > RESEARCH CATEGORIES
- > PUBLICATION TYPE
- ▼ SOURCE TITLE
 - Register Journal 314
 - > JOURNAL LIST
 - > OPEN ACCESS

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Register Journal

Publications 314 **Datasets** 0

SNIP - SJR -

PUBLICATIONS 314 **DATASETS** 0 **GRANTS** selected filter not applicable **PATENTS** selected filter not applicable **CLINICAL TRIALS** selected filter not applicable

POLICY DOCUMENTS selected filter not applicable

Show abstract Sort by: Publication Date ▼

Title, Author(s), Bibliographic reference - About the metrics

EFL Teachers' Beliefs and ICT Integration Practices During Distance Learning: Employing Replacement, Amplification, and Transformation Framework
Anggi Purwa Lestarina, Joko Nurkamto Nurkamto, Ngadiso Ngadiso Ngadiso
2022, Register Journal - Article

Technology is successfully integrated when technology makes learning effective, efficient, and creative.

ANALYTICAL VIEWS

RESEARCH CATEGORIES

- 47 Language, Communication and Culture 2
- 4704 Linguistics 10
- 39 Education 1
- 3901 Curriculum and Pedagogy 1
- 4703 Language Studies 1

OVERVIEW

Citations 330 Citations (Mean) 1.05

200
100
0

2013 2014 2015 2016 2017 2018 2019 2020 2021 2022

◆ Publications (total)

Indexing tinggi

- Scopus
- SSCI/SCIE/AHCI WoS

8 Strategi minimalis mengantarkan jurnal agar bisa terindeks scopus

1. Perhatikan H-index penulis, semakin tinggi H-Index scopus id nya semakin baik. Ada juga gagasan menarik misalnya di jurnal Automotive Experiences untuk menarik partisipasi penulis yang hebat dan keren dalam authorship jika author H-Index scopus id nya 15 ke atas boleh lah dikasih fasilitas gratis APC.
2. Perhatikan H-index Editor harus lebih tinggi daripada reviewernya. ada pandangan umum bahwa di Indonesia itu reviewer itu lebih tinggi kedudukannya dari editor sedangkan di luar negeri berbeda. misalnya di Journal of Pragmatics yang Q1 : <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-pragmatics>. isinya adalah editor dan jika ada reviewer dibahasakan review editor. contoh yang baik ialah Editor in Chief yang H-Index lumayan tinggi ialah EIC SiELE yang terindeks scopus Q1, EIC nya Ibu Prof. Dr. Yunisrina Qismullah Yusuf, M.Ling., memiliki H index 8 di Scopus id nya. kesimpulannya editor jurnal yang baik juga harus memperbaiki diri menjadi penulis yang baik. jangan hanya reject-reject tapi nggak pernah nulis. hmhhh gue banget :) :D

- 3. Cek H-index/sitasi jurnal. ini masih debatable karena ada yang berpendapat besarnya jumlah sitasi akan menentukan setidaknya 25 persen performa standing sebuah jurnal untuk dilirik team CSAB Scopus dan di sisi yang lain scopus citedness kecil tidak masalah asal ada aspek lain yang menonjol. contohnya ada jurnal-jurnal yang ketika apply ke scopus, scopus citedness relatif kecil atau sedikit seperti Samarah: Jurnal Hukum Keluarga dan Hukum Islam (ar-raniry.ac.id) atau Islamic Guidance and Counseling Journal (iainnumetrolampung.ac.id) tapi bisa terindeks karena aspek focus n scope yang super spesialis, grammar yang baik dan mutu artikel yang high quality merata pada jurnal-jurnal tersebut.

- 4. Keunikan focus and scope jurnal/super spesialis. team CSAB Scopus biasa mereject jurnal yang aim and scope sudah ada contohnya di jurnal yang terindeks scopus.
- 5. Konsistensi antara focus in scope dan artikel yg diterbitkan. Misalnya disebutkan sebuah jurnal adalah kajian hukum Islam di asia tenggara tetapi author hanya dari indonesia; berarti tidak sesuai yang dinyatakan di deskripsi jurnal dan focus and scope dengan kenyataannya.
- 6. Perwakilan editor minimal dari 3 benua (tips dr Prof. Istadi)
- 7. Artikel yang diterbitkan dalam Bahasa Inggris wajib di-proofread oleh native speaker. Google translate, Grammarly, Quillbot saja tidak cukup. Perlu human editor idealnya native speakers dan ahli dibidang ilmu yang diproofread.
- 8. Berdoa, tahajjud, dan banyak sedekah ini yang utama, guys!. usaha bumi itu 10%, usaha langit 90 persen. Allahumma scopus accepted. Aamiin.
- [PegiatJurnal.com: 8 Strategi minimalis mengantarkan jurnal agar bisa terindeks scopus](https://PegiatJurnal.com)

link men-submit jurnal ke scopus:

- <https://suggestor.step.scopus.com/suggestTitle/step1.cfm>

pengalaman jurnal ahkam terindeks scopus dalam 2 bulan

- [PDF Materi \(File responses\) - Google Drive](#)

Cara mendaftarkan jurnal ke web of science

- Yth. Bapak dan ibu Pengelola Jurnal
- Berikut ini adalah Update 2021 atau Info Terkini Cara mudah Submit Jurnal ke Clarivate Web of Science: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Maycjw2HFY4> atau ke link URL ini: <http://www.pegiatjurnal.com/2021/09/link-url-mendaftarkan-jurnal-ke-wos.html>

Terima kasih

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